

SDO-FM

A Multi-Modal Foundation Model POC for SDO Milestone 1

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RE: 23-SMDSS23-0074, SDO-FM: A Multi-Modal Foundation Model POC for SDO
(Grant#: 80NSSC24K0701) [Feb 26, 2024 - July 25, 2024]

Summary: This report summarizes the work completed on SDO-FM during the initial phase including clarification of the technical requirements and validation use cases.

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SDO-FM

A Multi-Modal Foundation Model POC for SDO

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1. Project Overview

The Solar Dynamics Observatory (SDO) is a NASA mission to understand the influence of the Sun on the Earth and near-Earth space by studying the solar atmosphere in extreme detail. SDO hosts three scientific experiments: Atmospheric Imaging Assembly (AIA), EUV Variability Experiment (EVE), Helioseismic and Magnetic Imager (HMI) that combine to offer an unprecedented view of our closest star over a broad range of wavelengths.

This combination of multiple instruments and a large temporal baseline make it an ideal candidate to test the potential of a multi-modal foundation model for scientific use-cases.

SDO-FM represents a new category of machine learning model using unsupervised machine learning methods with large-scale data sampling so that it is generalizable for a large range of downstream use-cases. It is thought that this kind of Foundation model could potentially become a useful asset for the heliophysics community - although this has yet to be determined. Its downstream usefulness is one of the additional outcomes of this study.

This project is an initial **SDO-FM Version A** designed to explore key concepts at a relatively small scale, leveraging prior efforts of FDL, including a data ingestion pipeline and existing validation use-cases.

The concept of approach is shown on the diagram below, which shows how the development of SDO-FM Version A begins with identification of the validation cases and criteria. These are the proven ML workflows that SDO-FM will be benchmarked against and represent the first project Milestone. The second Milestone is the completion of a testing pipeline, which allows unsupervised architectures to be tested in a highly iterative way. Within the testing pipeline is also the data pipeline, which serves SDO data at a resolution and cadence suitable for the validation cases. Lastly, the period up to Milestone 3 describes an evaluation and iteration step, where the model is compared against the validation use-cases. Note that for SDO-FM Version A, due to its relatively small size, we are expecting a relatively narrow spread of application (known as generalizability). Ideally,

this approach can be repeated with enriched sampling and increased parameters each time for versions SDO-FM B, C, in due course.

The expectation is that with increased sampling resolution at each version, subsequent iterations will become increasingly capable.

Figure 1: The Concept of Approach for SDO-FM A

For SDO-FM Version A, we expect trade-offs in efficacy and therefore are working with the heliophysics advisory to select validation cases that are closely adjacent - that is, they leverage similar input data and sampling strategies. If SDO-FM A is able to successfully emulate the validation cases, it will show the viability of this kind of foundational asset to service multiple use-cases. SDO-FM A will be released to the community with ‘recipes’ to enable this initial model to be evaluated.

2. Validation use-cases for SDO-FM A

Validating generalization and generative capabilities

Through several meetings with domain and SDO instrument experts, we have identified two ‘safe’ and one ‘stretch’ validation use-cases to implement in version A. The safe cases meet the requirements of being ‘close adjacent’ validation cases of proven ML pipelines that can be used to compare the performance of SDO-FM. The goal of building the foundation model around these narrow cases is to provide a proof of concept of **generalization** for the June 5-6 Science meeting where additional, scientifically meaningful use-cases will be then identified. The stretch demo case helps understand the potential of the foundation model to encapsulate knowledge of the Sun in the embedding space and is a first big test of the SDO-FM’s **generative** capabilities.

Autocalibration (Safe Validation)	Recreate Virtual EVE (Safe Validation)	Generative EVE (Stretch demo)
<p>Can we reconstruct the AIA multi-channel degradation curves of 2010–2020 and compare them with the sounding-rocket based degradation curves for a better performing, lower cost solution?</p>	<p>Can we demonstrate that SDO-FM can capture multi channel temperature relationships within AIA data by reproducing Virtual-EVE pipelines to generate synthetic MEGS-A irradiance measurements from 2010 - 2014? Compare both ground truth (pre-2014) and synthetic now-casting results (post 2014).</p>	<p>Can we use the learned embedding space to generate predictive virtual EVE (MEGS-A/B)? Can this show that the model can capture the multi thermal physics within embedding space.</p>
<p>What is the physical effect?</p> <p>The SDO EUV channels degrade in the presence of the emission they aim to measure. An apparent dimming is observed as a function of time in multiple EUV channels, and inhibits long-term studies. A FM should be able to pick up these long-term degradation trends in the dataset</p>	<p>What is the physical effect?</p> <p>The SDO observes the Sun as both narrow-band images (SDO/AIA) and as sun-as-a-star spectra (SDO/EVE).</p> <p>Both instruments observe the same plasma distribution. The FM should be able to understand the contributions from solar features on the EUV spectra.</p>	<p>What is the physical effect?</p> <p>The SDO observes the Sun as both narrow-band images (SDO/AIA) and as sun-as-a-star spectra (SDO/EVE).</p> <p>Both instruments observe the same plasma distribution, and the FM should be able to understand the contributions from specific solar features on the EUV spectra.</p>
<p>Data requirements</p> <p>SDOML(AIA), old correction tables</p>	<p>Data requirements</p> <p>SDOML (AIA, EVE MEGS-A)</p>	<p>Data requirements</p> <p>SDOML (AIA, EVE [MEGS-A/B])</p>
<p>Sampling requirements</p> <p>Once per day or less. 1 in 120 cadence from SDOML</p>	<p>Sampling requirements</p> <p>At least once per hour ,1 in 5 cadence from SDOML</p>	<p>Sampling requirements</p> <p>At least once per hour ,1 in 5 cadence from SDOML</p>
<p>What is SOTA using classical methods?</p> <p>LMSAL performs calibration with sounding rocket flights, which is expensive and technically demanding</p>	<p>What is SOTA using classical methods?</p> <p>A linear model can account for a large portion of this relationship., A CNN is used to correct for outlier events such as flares.</p>	<p>What is SOTA using classical methods?</p> <p>A linear model can account for a large portion of this relationship. A CNN is used to correct for outlier events such as flares.</p>
<p>What improvements are we looking for?</p> <p>Reproducing the results from 2021 with greater efficiency in terms of data required and computational resources.</p>	<p>What improvements are we looking for?</p> <p>Better performing model than from 2018 (with respect to metrics). Demonstrate physics described within model embedding space.</p>	<p>What improvements are we looking for?</p> <p>Agreement with MEGS-B during present-day observations</p>
<p>What would validation look like?</p> <p>Detailed examination of generated images with comparison to SOTA calibration pipelines, intensity histograms, data spike analysis, etc.</p>	<p>What would validation look like?</p> <p>Comparison to SDO/EVE MEGS-A during its operation (2010-2014). Using Virtual EVE pipeline to demonstrate irradiance reconstruction.</p>	<p>What would validation look like?</p> <p>Comparison to MEGS-B and agreement during present-day. Using Virtual EVE pipeline to demonstrate irradiance reconstruction.</p>

3. Technical Requirements

3.1 Prototype Foundation Model

ConvTransform2D as used in the Neck ([source](#))

- FM is split into three components:
 - **Backbone**: This is the core model the result of which provides pretrained embeddings
 - **Neck**: transforms the token-based output of transformer into a single embedding suitable for processing with standard layers.
 - **Head**: This is the fine-tuning model, they are interchangeable depending on the final expected task.
- Our development platform contains testing apparatus for backbones of architectures:
 - Masked autoencoder (MAE)
 - SWIN3D
 - A custom solar-aware masked autoencoder that biases masking towards areas of high solar activity (SAMAE)

3.1a Data Ingestion

- **SDOMLv2a** has been loaded and a data loader generalized from the work of FDL-X 2023
- Space Weather Prediction Centre reports have been used to generate a flaring database and determine distribution for bias in Solar-Aware MAE case.
- We're aware we may need to collect higher cadence data for any downstream tasks that involve flaring. We'd like to start with what we already have and then append these later. There is a ML-question on how to best implement the changed modality of higher cadence (as well for potentially spatial resolution).

3.1b Data Preprocessing

Guyou hemisphere-in-a-square projection as an example of what an alternative view of the sun could look like for training ([source](#))

- SDO data is brought to level 1.5 in previous works (Galvez et al 2019, Fawcett et al 2023).
- AIA & HMI data is masked to contain only the solar limb.
- There is a science-question on whether an alternative projection would be acceptable for training, something we'd like to test later.

3.1c Analysis Ready Data

- SDO data is brought to level 1.5 in previous works (Galvez et al 2019, Fawcett et al 2023).

3.1d Test bench

- The benchmarking tooling has begun in the form of predominantly reconstruction loss. These will be reported during model evaluation.
- Each downstream task requires suitable evaluation and hence each will require metrics.

3.1d Model Training

- Model training is currently occurring via GPUs on Google Cloud at 14 hrs per epoch for the following construction:
 - Solar-aware MAE
 - 32.2M total trainable parameters
 - Final embedding dimension of 128
 - Temporal window of 1 hour (5x12 min frames) with a tubelet size of 5.
- Efforts are currently underway to increase the training speed via TPUs however proving difficult to debug.

3.1e Model Deployment and Inference

- Model weights are stored in a Google bucket for the time being whilst development continues.

3.1f Validation and Analysis.

- Final validation will come from the complete comparison of:
 - reconstruction loss of the backbone

- fine-tuned model value in time and accuracy

3.1g SDO-FM Cookbook (Documentation)

- The SDO-FM Cookbook will provide an overview of the validation use-cases used to build the prototype. It will provide scientific researchers with a series of recipes on how to design experiments with insights on key components including sampling strategies, incorporating diverse data, physics, data status and validation plans.

4. Engaging the Scientific Community

SDO-FM is being built in close collaboration with the scientific community in a two-way co-learning process. The engineering process is guided by the science advisory in determining feasible and meaningful validation use-cases to base the initial prototype model on. While in parallel, the team is building documentation and a foundation model cookbook that will provide guidance to the scientific community on the process of building the model, the scientific meaning of validation and outcomes and a series of recipes for expanding the model to increasingly generative capabilities in the future.

In addition to building the documentation and cookbook meta learning process, we are engaging the scientific community through a series of meetings in which we both update on progress and invite feedback and insights to inform next steps.

At our general science meeting on June 5th-6th (9am- 12pm EST) we invite the greater science community to engage in rich discussions about the potential for SDO-FM. Please contact (anne@trillium.tech) for more information.

5. References & Citations

[1] Wright, P. J., Cheung, M. C. M., Eajat, T., Galvez, R., Szenicer, A., Meng, J., Muñoz-Jaramillo, A., & Fouhey, D. (2019). *DeepEM: Demonstrating a Deep Learning Approach to DEM Inversion*. Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/record/2587015>

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